

Supporting Information

Intrinsic controls on the kinetics of calcium extraction from crystalline slags: Implications on CO₂ mineralization

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Figure S2. Plots of natural logarithm of Ca reacted, $\ln X_{Ca}$, as a function of natural logarithm of time for deionized water at (a) 25 °C, (b) 45 °C, and (c) 90 °C, under static conditions, and (d) at 25 °C under stirred conditions. The linear relationship between the two variables indicates a power law dependence of Ca reacted in time. Dashed lines represent best-fit curves for a constant slope (i.e., power in time) of 0.1 for 25 and 45 °C and 0.2 for 90 °C. Fitting was carried out using the equations mentioned in each plot, for the entire data range until decreases in dissolved Ca became evident, presumably from the precipitation of Ca-silicate phases.

Figure S3. Ca, Si, Al, Na, Mg, Fe, and Mn in solution as a function of time in deionized water at 25 °C for 6 slag types.

Figure S4. Representative photomicrographs under (a) plane-polarized and (b) cross-polarized light of an air-cooled blast furnace slag sample before dissolution, showing the dominance of melilite having grain sizes exceeding 0.5 mm. Melilite is characterized by its first-order gray to anomalous blue interference color, and its prismatic to tabular grain morphology.⁴⁹

Figure S5. Plots of natural logarithm of Ca reacted, $\ln X_{Ca}$, as a function of natural logarithm of time for experiments carried out in (a), (b), (c) 5% acetic acid at (a) 25 °C, (b) 45 °C, and (c) 90 °C, and (d) 1% acetic acid at 90 °C. Plateaus in X_{Ca} at later times were observed as Ca extraction from the slag approaches completion, i.e., the fraction of Ca reacted approaches ~ 1 at the longer reaction times, and for the fast-dissolving slags.

Figure S6. Ca in solution as a function of time in sodium EDTA at 45 °C for 6 slag types.

Figure S7. Calcium release over time for (a) electric arc furnace, (b) basic oxygen furnace, (c) air-cooled blast furnace, (d) co-mingled electric arc furnace, (e) stainless steel, and (f) ladle slag under static (open symbols) and stirred (closed symbols) conditions at ~25 °C.

Table S1. Specific surface area and d_{50} of the slags estimated from the particle size distributions.

Slag type	Particle size fraction (μm)	d_{50} (μm)	Specific surface area (cm^2/g)	
EAF	~5	7.7	4634.5	
	<38	31.1	982.5	
	38-53		51.1	667.8
			41.1*	831.0*
	53-106	101.1	313.9	
	106-150	125.8	245.7	
BOF	38-53	57.8	612.7	
	106-150	133.1	83.0	
ac-BF	38-53	47.9	722.4	
		52.8*	819.2*	
cm-EAF	106-150	116.2	119.5	
	38-53	47.9	845.7	
SS	38-53	41.1	902.5	
LS	38-53	46.5	798.0	

*Values from repeat preparation of sample

Table S2. Semi-quantitative analysis of various minerals that are present in the slags obtained using X-ray diffraction.

Mineral	Chemical Formula	Silicate structure	EAF	BOF	Air-cooled BF	Co-mingled EAF	SS	LS
Larnite ($\beta\text{-C}_2\text{S}$)	Ca_2SiO_4	Nesosilicate	••••	••••	-	•••	-	•
Larnite ($\gamma\text{-C}_2\text{S}$)	Ca_2SiO_4	Nesosilicate	-	-	-	•	•••	•••
Brownmillerite	$\text{Ca}_2(\text{Al},\text{Fe})_2\text{O}_5$		•••	••	-	-	-	-
Magnetite	Fe_3O_4		••••	••	-	-	-	-
Wüstite	$(\text{Fe},\text{Mn},\text{Mg})\text{O}$		••	•••	-	••••	•	•
Merwinite	$\text{Ca}_3\text{MgSi}_2\text{O}_8$	Nesosilicate	-	•	•	•	•	•
Melilite	$\text{Ca}_2(\text{Mg},\text{Al})(\text{Al},\text{Si})\text{SiO}_7$	Sorosilicate	-	•	••••	•	-	-
Kirschsteinite	$\text{Ca}(\text{Fe},\text{Mg})\text{SiO}_4$	Nesosilicate	-	••	-	-	-	-
Srebrodskite	$\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$		-	-	-	•	•	-
Portlandite	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$		-	•	-	-	-	-
Gypsum	$\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$		-	-	•	-	-	-
Perovskite	CaTiO_3		-	-	•	-	-	-
Mayenite	$\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$		-	-	-	•	-	•
Spinel	$\text{MgO}(\text{Al},\text{Fe})_2\text{O}_3$		-	-	-	••	-	-
Cuspidine	$\text{Ca}_4\text{F}_2\text{SiO}_7$	Sorosilicate	-	-	-	•	••••	•••
Bredigite	$\text{Ca}_7\text{MgSi}_4\text{O}_{16}$	Nesosilicate	-	-	-	•	-	•
Fluorite	CaF_2		-	-	-	-	•	•
Brucite	$\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$		-	-	-	-	•	-
Monohydrocalcite	$\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		-	-	-	-	••	-
Calcite	CaCO_3		•	•	•	•	•••	••
Dolomite	$\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$		-	-	-	•	-	-
Periclase	MgO		-	•	-	-	-	-
Quartz	SiO_2	Tectosilicate	-	-	-	-	-	•

Quantity of • symbols is proportional to the relative abundance of the phase. Estimated abundances are: ••••: >30%, •••: 20-30%; ••: 10-20%; •: <10%. Symbol - denotes absence of the phase.

Table S3. Chemical composition of the six slag types in mass % of oxide as obtained by X-ray fluorescence.

	EAF	BOF	Air-cooled BF	Co-mingled EAF	SS	LS
CaO	32.3	38.4	36.0	35.2	48.7	43.2
MgO	6.7	5.6	9.0	8.0	7.3	8.9
Al ₂ O ₃	6.9	5.0	8.6	10.7	1.5	3.9
SiO ₂	12.6	13.7	32.0	15.4	26.3	21.7
SO ₃	0.5	0.3	2.6	0.8	0.3	3.1
Cr ₂ O ₃	3.5	2.3	2.0	3.0	4.0	2.4
MnO	4.8	3.5	0.5	5.3	1.2	1.6
Fe ₂ O ₃	30.8	28.8	4.8	20.4	5.9	10.5
LOI	0.6	1.2	2.3	0.2	4.1	3.8